

Chapter 4

Determinants of Risk Disclosures an Evidence from Sri Lankan Manufacturing Companies

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Abstract

Purpose:

The need for companies to provide a higher level of disclosure has grown as a result of the business environment, operations, and regulatory requirements becoming more complicated. The main risks that listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka have disclosed are examined in this paper, along with the board characteristics that are associated with the disclosure of corporate risk information.

Design/methodology:

Sample of this study consist of randomly selected 30 listed manufacturing entities from the Colombo Stock Exchange for the period of five years (2013-2017). 150 firm-year observations were analyzed using panel regression techniques. Risk disclosure was measured by developing a 37-item risk disclosure index based on Shrives & Linsley, (2006). The variables included in the study are board size, board independence, and role duality and ownership concentration.

Findings:

According to the analysis of the risk disclosures, the level of risk disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka tends to increase over time; total risk disclosure rose from 28.5% in 2013 to 32.3% in 2017. According to the research, there is also a significant correlation between board size, role duality, and ownership concentration and risk disclosure practices in Sri Lankan listed manufacturing companies.

Implications:

This study's sample size is modest and consists solely of publicly traded manufacturing firms. Only published, audited annual reports were used in this research to gather data. In addition to board size, board independence, role diversity, and ownership concentration, and can suggest other corporate

governance variables for consideration. The best study can be obtained by using secretarial reports of businesses.

Originality/value:

This is the first study on risk disclosure practices of manufacturing sector companies in Sri Lanka. This study measures the level of risk disclosure variance over time and the impact of board characteristics on risk disclosure practices.

Key words: *Risk Disclosures, Risk Disclosure Index, Manufacturing Firms, Content Analysis, Corporate Governance*

Introduction

Background of the Study

Corporate governance is the system of directing and controlling an organization towards achieving its desired goals and objectives (Shah & Napier, 2015). Corporate governance is a set of relationships between a company's directors, its shareholders, and other stakeholders. It also provides the structure through which the objectives of the company are set, and the means of achieving those objectives and monitoring performance, are determined (*OECD Principles of Corporate Governance, 2015*). Corporate governance is a widely accepted concept. For an organization to pursue its strategy in an ethical and effective way and offer safeguards against the misuse of resources, human, financial, physical or intellectual (Shah & Napier, 2015). The board of directors are responsible for the governance of their organization (Donnelly & Mulcahy, 2008). In corporate governance, shareholders' part is to appoint directors and the auditors in order to establish an appropriate corporate governance structure in a particular organization. The responsibility of board of directors relating to the organization is to setting up strategic goals, to govern them to determine whether they have accomplished, to manage the business process and to report to the shareholders regarding their management (*Code of Best Practice on Corporate Governance, 2013*). Therefore, the corporate governance is all about what the board of directors of the organization is doing and how it enhances the value of the organization.

Risk disclosures play a vital role in determining the safety level of a particular investment, helps to identify liquidation positions under certain market conditions and also about the leverage condition of the company which will lead to a great impact on investment decision of an investor. According to the Code of Best Practice on Corporate Governance of 2013 together with the Securities and Exchange Commission of Sri Lanka (SEC) and The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Sri Lanka (ICASL), it is essential to disclose about the risk that the firm will face.

However, for non-listed firms there is no legislation for risk disclosure but disclosing risk may gain an additional advantage for that particular firm in their business operations.

Research Problem

In many countries such as India, Australia, Malaysia, Spanish and European countries contexts it has conducted many researches to explain the association between determinants of corporate governance and risk disclosure practices (Abdul Samad, 2004; Elzahar & Hussainey, 2012; Gallery et al., 2015; Saggar & Singh, 2017). For example in Australian context they have found that how board of directors' characteristics, the influence of the Audit Committee, the influence of other board committees, external auditing oversight and quality, institutional shareholders and corporate risk factors affect in disclosing risks (Gallery et al., 2015). In Egyptian context they have found that how competition, board size, role duality, ownership concentration, firm size and liquidity have affected on disclosing risks to non-financial institutions (Samaha et al., 2015).

In Sri Lankan context researches have only conducted in banking, insurance and financial institutions to find out the determining factors in exercising a good risk disclosure practices (Abeywardana & Panditharathna, 2016). In here I have found that in Sri Lankan context there are no researches has conducted in finding the risk disclosing practices particularly in manufacturing sector companies so far. Therefore, this is my research gap which is I'm going to fill for my research purpose. In this study I hope to identify the influence of several corporate governance factors in determining the level and the extent of the risk disclosures by manufacturing companies listed in Sri Lanka Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE). Therefore I suppose to find out how manufacturing sector companies has disclosed their potential risks in their annual reports for the period of five years (2013 – 2017) with the assistance of risk disclosure index and to identify the factors that specifically affect in disclosing risk.

Research Question

This research study considers the authentic influence of determinants of the corporate governance on risk disclosure practice in the manufacturing sector of Sri Lanka. Therefore, the research paper addresses one vital research question as,

- 1 Does corporate governance improve risk disclosure of listed entities in Sri Lanka?

Research Objectives

This study specially identified and scrutinized following objectives.

- 1 To identify the level of risk disclosure in listed entities.
- 2 To investigate the impact of board attributes on risk disclosure of listed entities.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

Various theories support the provision of risk information. Agency theory hold that provision of information is essential in decision making process and can work as monitoring mechanism for shareholders and investors over manager's activities (Bonazzi & Islam, 2007). The agency theory used to explain the association between agents and principals (Florackis, 2008). The agents represent the principals in a particular business transaction and they are expect to represent the best interests of the principal's disregard for their self-interest (McKnight & Weir, 2009). Due to the different interests of principals and agents it may become a source of conflict. The resulting miscommunication and disagreement of interests may result in various problems within companies (Mustapha & Che Ahmad, 2011). Corporate governance can be used to mitigate the conflict between agents and principals and to change the rules which the agent operates and restore the principal's interests (Namazi & Kermani, 2013). To enhance the board effectiveness in relation to mitigate the agency cost, appointing outside as well as independent directors with experience at industry level will further helps in improving board effectiveness (Badu & Appiah, 2017).

Institutional Environment in Sri Lanka

The risk management evolve globally in several aspects of business operations and activities. Corporate governance and risk management increasingly intertwined. There is a mutual impact of corporate governance choices on risk management strategies and disclosures (Lajili, 2009). Increase of demand for risk reporting had led to reform number of regulators. International financial reporting standards 7 (IFRS 7) financial instruments and Sri Lanka Auditing Standards (SLAuS 540) which includes greater measures on risk transparency and disclosure which enhance the market discipline in disclosing informative risk disclosures. (Maghzom et al., 2016).

Corporate Governance

Corporate governance mechanisms categorized as internal mechanisms (board size, board independence and board of directors) and external mechanisms (competitive market conditions and market for managerial labor) (Zabri et al., 2016). According to the study of Chen & Liu, (2013) the governance disclosures plays a weak role in reducing the cost of capital in Asian emerging markets. In Sri Lanka there is no any Rule to guide the Corporate Governance regarding PLC's, hence all the PLC's just put the same corporate governance note in every years annual report. However, consider about the Financial Institutions including all the Banks those statements will audited by the both external auditor and Central Bank of Sri Lanka. However even in PLC's use the guidelines provided by code of best practices.

Risk Disclosure

Risk disclosure is a pivotal aspect of business risks where risk reporting offers a greater transparency and enhances investors' confidence (Abraham & Cox, 2007; Hassan et al., 2008; Shrikes & Linsley, 2006). Disclosing risk information about financial risks is very important since it enhance the transparency, giving shareholders more confidence and lowering their uncertainty about future cash flows. Risk is unavoidable element of any business enterprise. The risks can be classified basically into two parts. Financial risks are mandatory risks (credit, liquidity, interest rate, exchange rate and price risk) while non-financial risks are voluntary risks (operations, strategic, integrity, empowerment, information technology and processing risks). Risk information can help in reducing the cost of capital and allow companies to represent that they are aware of the risks faced by them and have put systems in place to manage these risks (Shrikes & Linsley, 2006).

Determinants of Risk Disclosure

The quality of corporate risk disclosure is driven by several corporate governance factors such as board size, board diversity, and presence of independent and nonexecutive directors on the board and ownership concentration (Abdul Samad, 2004). At the same time there are several factors such as firm size, leverage, profitability, industrial sector, audit environment and level of risk which are significantly correlated with corporate risk disclosure (Dobler et al., 2011).

Comparison between Developing and Developed Countries Practices

While a considerable body of literature reflects detailed academic work on disclosures concerning corporate governance, there is limited research on corporate

risk disclosures (Lajili, 2009). The risk disclosing practices are somewhat different across various countries. Developing countries, which are economically more vulnerable, might, thus, be benefited by implementing international disclosure standards. The majority of risk disclosure studies is limited to developed countries (Lajili, 2009). By using the comprehensive section of company annual reports in Malaysia, Hassan et al., (2008) has found that risk disclosure levels in Malaysian annual reports contain much less information than in the UK annual reports despite with regulatory requirements.

In the context of developing countries, according to an analysis of listed banks in Bangladesh, it has significantly improved their risk disclosure over time, primarily on voluntary basis. In here the results has showed that the operational risk information category has taken a highest risk disclosing level, where the lowest is in market risk information. Elshandidy & Neri, (2015) found that there is a significant variation in mandatory and voluntary risk disclosures within and between firms across German, UK and US countries. Further, according to the Elshandidy & Neri, (2015) findings, the governance factors in UK strictly influenced in disclosing voluntary risks rather than mandatory risk disclosures, whereas in Italy it required to disclose mandatory risk disclosures rather than the voluntary risk disclosures. According to the Australian studies since 2007 there is a framework for Australian companies to provide risk disclosures as part of a broader corporate governance disclosure framework (Gallery et al., 2015).

Conceptualization and Hypothesis Development

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Hypothesis Development

H1: There is a significant positive association between board size and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

H2: There is a significant positive association between board independency and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

H3: There is a significant negative association between role duality and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

H4: There is a significant negative association between ownership concentration and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Board Size and Risk Disclosure

The board size is measured by the number of directors on a company's board (Kakanda et al., 2017). While some studies find no association between board size

and risk disclosure (Elzahar & Hussainey, 2012) the other risk disclosure studies found that board size positively and significantly associate with disclosure of voluntary risk information (Elshandidy & Neri, 2015; Mousa & Elamir, 2013; Ntim et al., 2013; Said Mokhtar & Mellett, 2013). However, according to Cheng & Courtenay, (2006) there is an insignificant association between the board size and voluntary disclosures. Since the disclosure of information by a company is in the hands of the board members, when the larger the boards disseminate more risk information. In Sri Lankan context for a listed company in the Colombo Stock Exchange there should be at least two directors. However, according to the prior studies, most of them have found that there is a positive association between board size and risk disclosures. Therefore for this study purpose also it supposed to develop a hypothesis as follows.

H1: There is a significant positive association between board size and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Board Independency and Risk Disclosure

Board independency refers to the proportion of total number of non-executive directors to the total number of directors to the board (Prabowo & Simpson, 2011). Independent directors are important in making risk information publicly known to investors. This association has been tested by several researches and according to their findings (Craig et al., 2011; Lajili, 2009; Ntim et al., 2013) provided evidence with favor of this association. However, Allini et al., (2016); Elzahar & Hussainey, (2012) was not in favor with this statement. Some studies have support that there is an insignificant association between the presence of independent directors and voluntary disclosure (Maher et al., 2008; Mohamad & Sulong, 2010) including corporate social responsibility disclosure (Majeed et al., 2015). However in contrast with the statement above mentioned, many studies has found that there is a positive significant effect on presence of independent (non-executive) directors on risk disclosure (C. J. P. Chen & Jaggi, 2000; Elzahar & Hussainey, 2012; Lajili, 2009; Lopes & Rodrigues, 2007; Samaha et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2013). Since many studies have justified, for my study purpose also I consider that there is a significant positive association between the proportions of independent (non-executive) directors in the board with the extent of disclosing risks.

H2: There is a significant positive association between board independency and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Role Duality and Risk Disclosure

The structure of board is an important corporate governance mechanism. Role duality is a situation where there is no separation between decision control and decision management (Elshandidy & Neri, 2015). According to prior empirical studies it shows mix results of the association between role duality and voluntary disclosures. There are some studies which has found that there is an insignificant association between CEO duality and the extent of voluntary disclosures (Cheng & Courtenay, 2006; Sarikhani & Ebrahimi, 2011). In the risk disclosure scenario, recent studies has found that there is no significant association between role duality and voluntary risk disclosures (Elzahar & Hussainey, 2012; Moumen et al., 2016; Mousa & Elamir, 2013; Ntim et al., 2013; Said Mokhtar & Mellett, 2013). However there are several studies which has been revealed a negative association between role duality and voluntary disclosure (Khlif & Hussainey, 2014; Wang et al., 2013).

Since the findings of the prior studies are mixed, it is hard to define a certain association between role duality and risk disclosure. However, for my study purpose it develops a hypothesis as follows.

H3: There is a significant negative association between role duality and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Ownership Concentration and Risk Disclosure

Ownership concentration refers to the proportion of stock owned by individual investors and large-block. According to the empirical studies it has found that, though there is a negative association between ownership concentration and voluntary disclosure (Chau & Gray, 2002; Ghazali, 2007), the association between ownership concentration and voluntary risk information disclosure is indeterminate. According to Said Mokhtar & Mellett, (2013) they have found that there is a negative association between mandatory risk reporting and ownership concentration and there is an insignificant association between voluntary risk reporting (Mohobbot, 2005). However, based on Khan & Muttakin, (2013) study, since an increased ownership concentration requires less voluntary disclosure practices, it develops a hypothesis for this study purpose as follows. Further in here I consider the top 10 voting shareholders ownership percentage of the listed manufacturing organizations in the sample (Bai et al., 2004; Ma et al., 2010).

H4: There is a significant negative association between ownership concentration and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Methodology

Sample and Data

As the population for the study, has considered 298 companies representing 20 business sectors to the date of 29th June 2018 which are listed in the Colombo Stock Exchange. To examine the nature of the linkage between corporate governance mechanisms and risk disclosure empirically, it has selected a sample of manufacturing sector companies which are listed in Colombo Stock Exchange for the time period of five years (2013- 2017) annual reports to be considered for this study purpose with the focus on voluntary risk management disclosures. Among the following manufacturing companies, select a random sample of 30 companies which consist together with 150 observations for this study purpose.

The firms included in our sample had to comply with following two conditions. First, it had to belong to a manufacturing sector firms. Financial and companies (e.g. banks and insurance companies) were removed from the sample, since they have specific characteristics together with different framework for disclosure practices according to their regulations (Elshandidy & Neri, 2015; Liao & Lu, 2009; Ma et al., 2010). Second, this study focuses on annual reports disregard with other sources of information (Liao & Lu, 2009; Majeed et al., 2015). The sectors which belong to manufacturing sector has been list down as follows,

Table 6: Manufacturing sectors listed in Colombo Stock exchange

Sector	No of companies
Chemical and pharmaceuticals	10
Footwear and textile	2
Manufacturing	38
Beverage food and tobacco	21
Total	71

A name list of sample manufacturing firms listed in Colombo Stock Exchange is attached with appendix (refer Table 11).

Measurement of Independent Variables

Independent variables (Corporate governance factors) measured by as follows.

Table 7: Measurements of independent variables

Board size (BS)	Total number of directors in the board
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Board independency (BI)	The proportion of independent non-executive directors to total number of directors on the board.
Role duality (RDU)	Representation of as a chairman of the board and as a CEO.
Ownership concentration (OC)	Percentage of shares with the largest shareholders.

Measurement of Dependent Variables

Dependent variable (Risk disclosure) is measured by using a risk disclosure index which is adopted by Shrives & Linsley, (2006) model consisting with financial risks, operations risks, strategic risks, empowerment risks, integrity risks, and information processing and technology risks. There are several studies which have used the risk disclosure category index by Shrives & Linsley, (2006) for their study purpose as well (Abid & Shaiq, 2015; Moumen et al., 2016). In my study I supposed to use this model because, the study of Shrives & Linsley, (2006) carried out in United Kingdom. The regime for regulation of risk disclosures is voluntary in United Kingdom, which is similar to the Sri Lankan context. In Sri Lanka, there is no mandatory requirement for firms to report on non-financial risks and only mandatory requirement is to report financial risks. The risk disclosure index is attached in appendix (Figure 2).

Regression Model Specification

This study analyses the influence of corporate governance quality in the form of board characteristics which would have an impact on the extent of risk disclosures using multiple regressions. This study proposed a model as follows,

Total risk disclosure = f (corporate governance board characteristics)

$$RD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS + \beta_2 BI + \beta_3 RDU + \beta_4 OC + \varepsilon$$

Where the dependent variable is,

RD = Risk Disclosure The independent variables are,

BS = Board size

BI = Independency

RDU = Role duality

OC = Ownership concentration

ε = Error term

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics for Risk Disclosure

Table 8: Descriptive statistics for risk disclosure

Year	Max	Min	Mean	Std. deviation	Observations
Overall	21	4	31.242	13.357	150
2013	18	5	10.533	4.384	30
2014	21	5	11.8	4.787	30
2015	21	5	11.666	5.181	30
2016	21	4	11.9	5.241	30
2017	21	4	11.9	5.254	30

A summary of risk disclosure index (refer Table 6)

Table 03 shows that there are 30 manufacturing firms for consecutive five years period. Overall the risk disclosure practice in manufacturing firms has spread between 0.1081 and 0.5676. The maximum risk disclosure practice is conducting by Royal Ceramics Lanka (PLC) while the minimum number of risks has been disclosed by the Ceylon Tabaco Company (PLC).

When it analysis the flow of risk disclosure levels over time, there is a rapid growth in the level of risk disclosures. In 2013 it shows 10.533 % disclosure level of risks and 11.9% in 2017.

Descriptive Statistics for Independent Variables

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observations	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
Board size	150	3	15	8.06	2.1432
Board independency	150	0.1111	8	0.3825	0.1341
Role duality	150	0	1	0.0866	0.2822
Ownership concentration	150	0.2467	0.9819	0.8254	0.1143

The minimum number of three board members was represent in the board of Industrial Asphalts (Ceylon) PLC in the year of 2014. In the year of 2016, Haycarb PLC was representing the maximum number of 15 members as board of directors of the company. As an average there are 08 board members are exist in the manufacturing sector firms in Sri Lanka for the period of 2013-2017.

As a proportion to the total number of board members, Blue Diamonds Jewelry Worldwide (PLC) has both the maximum and minimum number of independent directors in the board. In the year of 2013 there were 4 independent non-executive directors out of 5 members in the board which represent the maximum of 08 in the descriptive statistics. However in 2015 and 2016 the Blue Diamond Jewelry Worldwide (PLC) was consist with 01 independent director in the board out of 09 directors which was represent as the minimum figure of 0.1111 in the above table.

There are few of Sri Lankan manufacturing sector firms which has one director who is performing the both roles of Chairman of the board and Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of the firm as well. Most of the manufacturing sector firms have separate roles over the control in Sri Lankan context.

There is maximum ownership concentration in ODEL (PLC) in the year of 2017 which was held 98.19% ownership from the first major ten shareholders of the company. At the same time in the year of 2014 Blue Diamond Jewelry (PLC) the first ten major shareholders represent 24.67% of minimum ownership concentration. In Sri Lankan context when it takes the first ten major shareholders’ ownership it represents a considerable average of 0.8254193.

Data screening

It has tested for missing values of the study and there are no missing values to find in this data set. The data set was inspected, but there was no any outliers of the study to be found. (Refer figure 3)

Regression assumption testing

Normality Test:

Table 10: Normality

Risk Disclosure

	Percentiles	Smallest		
1%	0.1081	0.1081		
5%	0.1351	0.1081		
10%	0.1351	0.1351	Obs	150
25%	0.1892	0.1351	Sum of Wgt.	150
50%	0.3108		Mean	0.312424
75%	0.4324	Largest		
90%	0.4865	0.5676	Std. Dev.	0.1335753
95%	0.5135	0.5676	Variance	0.0178424
99%	0.5676	0.5676	Skewness	0.0429393

		0.5676	Kurtosis	1.771626
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Considering the table 7, the skewness is less than ± 1 and Kurtosis is less than ± 3 in this study. It can be concluded that all the variables meet the acceptance criteria of skewness and kurtosis index. Hence there is a normality in this data set.

Heteroskedasticity Test:

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of risk disclosure

$$\text{chi2}(1) = 0.09$$

Prob > chi2 = 0.7686

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 it can accept the null hypothesis which state that the error variances are equal in this data set. Therefore, no need to robust the data set in order to remove the heteroscedasticity.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Analysis:

Table 11: Variance Inflation Factor Analysis

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Role duality	1.10	0.9116
Board independency	1.06	0.9391
Ownership Concentration	1.04	0.9601
Board size	1.01	0.9888
Mean VIF	1.05	

Since all the independent variables' VIF value is below to 10 it can said that there is no multicollinearity. Therefore, the multicollinearity assumption will not be violated and data set can be used for the further analysis.

Discussion of Correlation Analysis

Table 12: Correlation matrix

Risk Disclosure		Board Size	Boar Independency	Role Duality	Ownership Concentration
Risk Disclosure	1.0000				

Board Size	-0.0754	1.0000			
Board Independency	-0.0063	-0.0816	1.0000		
Role Duality	-0.0158	0.0690	-0.2363**	1.0000	
Ownership Concentration	0.0523	-0.0583	0.0743	-0.1926**	1.0000

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

As a conclusion it can be stated that at a 5% significant level there is a significant negative association between board independency and role duality as well as between the role duality and ownership concentration which explains the change in role duality negatively and significantly influence to the changes in ownership concentration and board independency.

Hausman Test:

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\begin{aligned} \text{chi2 (0)} &= (b-B)' [(V_b-V_B)^{-1}] (b-B) \\ &= 15.94 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Prob>chi2} = 0.0031$$

Since the probability value of the study is less than 0.05 then for this study use the fixed effect model.

Table 13: Fixed effect model

Fixed-effects (within) regression				Number of obs = 150 Number of groups = 30 Obs per group: Min = 5 Avg = 5.0 Max = 5		
Group variable: company						
R-sq: Within = 0.1383				F(5,115) = 4.66 Prob > F = 0.0016 P> t [95% Conf. Interval]		
Between = -		Std.Err.	t			
Overall = 0.0155						
corr(u_i, xb) = -0.9372						
Risk Disclosure	Coef.					
Board Size	0.3712392	0.1405759	2.64	0.009	0.0928108	0.6496676
Board Independency	1.784922	1.627234	1.10	0.275	-1.43802	5.007865
Role Duality	-2.027454	0.9021846	-2.25	0.027	-3.814344	-0.240563
Ownership Concentration	10.03392	3.642674	2.75	0.007	2.819149	17.2487
_cons	2003.219	3.214903	623.10	0.000	1996.851	2009.586
sigma_u	1.5079892					
sigma_e	1.4928024					
rh0	0.50506081	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				
F test that all u_i=0:	F(29, 115) = 0.56	Prob > F = 0.9648				

Table 9 present the result of logistic fixed effect generalized least square regression analysis which is based on the ratio for board size, board independency, role duality and ownership concentration. All the variables are statistically tested significantly at 5 percent level. The P value of the model is 0.0016 it indicates the reliability of independent variables to predict risk disclosure practice. The fixed effect model is significant at the 5% level of significant (0.0016). In this case the model explains 13.83% of risk disclosure practice variance in listed manufacturing sector firms in

Sri Lanka is explained by the board size, board independency, role duality and ownership concentration. The rest 86.17% of variance in risk disclosure is explained by the factors other than board size, board independency, role duality and ownership concentration. Since the independent I have used in here is not well defining the dependent variable of risk disclosures, this is not a much significant model to define risk disclosure practice in Sri Lankan manufacturing sector. The t values also show the importance of a variable in the model. In this case board size, role duality and ownership concentration are very important somehow ownership concentration is the most important independent variable in explaining risk disclosure practices.

$$RD = 2003.219 + 0.371BS + 1.784BI - 2.027RDU + 10.033OC + \varepsilon$$

Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Table 14: Summary of hypothesis results

Hypothesis	Accept / Reject
<i>H1: There is a significant positive association between board size and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.</i>	Accepted
<i>H2: There is a significant positive association between board independency and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.</i>	Rejected
<i>H3: There is a significant negative association between role duality and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.</i>	Accepted
<i>H4: There is a significant negative association between ownership concentration and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.</i>	Rejected

Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the above study, it answered the all the research questions and the discussion will always connect to the introduction by way of the research questions or hypotheses that posed and the literature reviewed related to the study.

Research Question:

Does corporate governance improve risk disclosure of listed entities in Sri Lanka?

Research Objectives:

1. To identify the level of risk disclosure in listed entities.
2. To investigate the impact of board attributes on risk disclosure of listed entities.

The level of risk disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka tend to increase over time. Further the study has found that there is significant impact of board size and role duality on risk disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. For further clarification of this statement, first consider about how the research objectives have achieved in this study, through risk disclosure practices in Sri Lanka.

The first objective of this study is to identify the level of risk disclosure in listed entities. According to this study, listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka has increased their level of risk disclosures compared with their consecutive years. The percentage of risk disclosure has increased from 28.47% in 2013 up to 32.16% in 2017. The level of risk disclosures are attached with the bottom of “Table 04: Summary of Risk Disclosure Index”. The average level of disclosing risk of manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka is 31.24%. In this study I adopt Shrikes & Linsley, (2006) risk disclosure category index to measure the level of risk disclosures. In both Sri Lankan and Pakistan context have disclosed more about financial risk disclosures since those are mandatory to disclose. Further operational risks and strategic risks also have disclosed up to a significant level in voluntary basis.

The second objective of this study is to investigate the impact of board attributes on risk disclosure of listed entities. To figure the objective out, need to test the each hypothesis separately.

Board Size and risk disclosure

H1: There is a significant positive association between board size and the extent of risk disclosure in listed manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

The study of Elzahar & Hussainey, (2012) has found that there is a positive influence on risk disclosure from larger boards with the association of increased managerial monitoring. It is worth to mention that, this study also consistent with the findings of Elshandidy & Neri, (2015); Mousa & Elamir, (2013); Ntim et al., (2013); Said Mokhtar & Mellett, (2013) stating that there is a positive and significant association between risk disclosure and board size.

Board Independency and Risk Disclosure

H2: There is a significant positive association between board independency and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

It has found that the extent of voluntary disclosure increases with the number of non-executive directors in the board Donnelly & Mulcahy, (2008). According to my model of study the positive association is not significant. Therefore, my hypothesis was rejected.

Role Duality and Risk Disclosure

H3: There is a significant negative association between role duality and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

Separation of the positions of the CEO and the board chairman supports to enhance the transparency and the extent of disclosures without hiding any unfavorable information (Khan & Muttakin, 2013). Aligned with Khlif & Hussainey, (2014); Wang et al., (2013) this study also shows a significant negative association between risk disclosure and role duality

Ownership Concentration and Risk Disclosure

H4: There is a significant negative association between ownership concentration and the extent of risk disclosure in manufacturing companies of Sri Lanka.

In order to agency theory greater level of ownership concentration leads to less information asymmetry (Ma et al., 2010). Along with Scholten, (2014) my study results in a positive association which is significant. However, most of the studies are there which contrary with the findings of this study (Chau & Gray, 2002; Ghazali, 2007).

Finally this study was able to find the solution to the research question of “Does corporate governance improve risk disclosure of listed entities in Sri Lanka?”. The level of risk disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka tend to increase over time. Further, the study has found that there is significant impact of board size and role duality on risk disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka.

Contributions of the Study

The paper contributes to the literature by providing initial understanding of corporate risk disclosure practices in Sri Lanka as it has not been studied in manufacturing sector in Sri Lanka before, to the best of our knowledge. Further, this research paper will help to law and policy makers of the manufacturing sector of Sri

Lanka. And this analysis assists to continue the level of risk disclosure compliance in benchmark firms of the current context. The study found the evidence of those determinants of risk disclosure and how the risk disclosure was affected by the corporate governance attributes.

Implications

According to this study, it has found that there is high level of disclosing mandatory risks (financial risks) in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. By increasing the number of directors would has a significant influence on enhancing the level of risk disclosures. Further managing separated roles of Chairman and Chief Executive Officer also would contribute to improve the quality and the extent of voluntary risk disclosures.

Limitations and Directions for Future Studies

This study used only secondary data (audited annual reports). Therefore, future researches can supposed to use also primary data. And this study sample consisted of few manufacturing companies over five years. The future researchers can be considered also non listed manufacturing companies. It is suitable to use secretarial reports of companies to get the best research. Can consider other corporate governance factors in addition to board size, board independency, role duality and ownership concentration to measure the corporate governance. Last but not least, the studies could proceed with this study using more econometrically advanced techniques such as instrumental variables.

Reference

- Abdul Samad, F. (2004). Corporate governance and ownership structure in the malaysian corporate sector. In *Corporate Governance* (Vol. 9, pp. 355–385). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-3732\(04\)09014-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-3732(04)09014-0)
- Abeywardana, N. L. E., & Panditharathna, K. M. (2016). The Extent and Determinants of Voluntary Disclosures in Annual Reports: Evidence from Banking and Finance Companies in Sri Lanka. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 5(4), p147. <https://doi.org/10.5430/afr.v5n4p147>
- Abid, A., & Shaiq, M. (2015). A Study of Risk Disclosures in the Annual Reports of Pakistani Companies: A Content Analysis. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(11), 14–24.
- Abraham, S., & Cox, P. (2007). Analysing the determinants of narrative risk information in UK FTSE 100 annual reports. *The British Accounting Review*, 39(3), 227–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2007.06.002>

- Allini, A., Rossi, F. M., & Hussainey, K. (2016). The board's role in risk disclosure: An exploratory study of Italian listed state-owned enterprises. *Public Money & Management*, 36(2), 113–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540962.2016.1118935>
- Badu, E., & Appiah, K. O. (2017). The effects of board experience and independence on mitigating agency conflict. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 7(4), 445–467. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-08-2016-0072>
- Bai, C.-E., Liu, Q., Lu, J., Song, F. M., & Zhang, J. (2004). Corporate governance and market valuation in China. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 32(4), 599–616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jce.2004.07.002>
- Bonazzi, L., & Islam, S. M. N. (2007). Agency theory and corporate governance: A study of the effectiveness of board in their monitoring of the CEO. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 2(1), 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17465660710733022>
- Chau, G. K., & Gray, S. J. (2002). Ownership structure and corporate voluntary disclosure in Hong Kong and Singapore. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 37(2), 247–265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7063\(02\)00153-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7063(02)00153-X)
- Chen, C. J. P., & Jaggi, B. (2000). Association between independent non-executive directors, family control and financial disclosures in Hong Kong. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 19(4), 285–310. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-4254\(00\)00015-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-4254(00)00015-6)
- Chen, C.-W., & Liu, V. W. (2013). Corporate governance under asymmetric information: Theory and evidence. *Economic Modelling*, 33, 280–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2013.04.010>
- Cheng, E. C. M., & Courtenay, S. (2006). *Board composition, regulatory regime and voluntary disclosure* (Vol. 41). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intacc.2006.07.001>
- Code of Best Practice on Corporate Governance*. (2013).
- Craig, R., Lima Rodrigues, L., & Oliveira, J. (2011). Risk-related disclosures by non-finance companies: Portuguese practices and disclosure characteristics. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 26(9), 817–839. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686901111171466>
- Dobler, M., Lajili, K., & Zéghal, D. (2011). Attributes of Corporate Risk Disclosure: An International Investigation in the Manufacturing Sector. *Journal of International Accounting Research*, 10(2), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.2308/jiar-10081>
- Donnelly, R., & Mulcahy, M. (2008). Board Structure, Ownership, and Voluntary Disclosure in Ireland. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 16(5), 416–429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2008.00692.x>

- Elshandidy, T., & Neri, L. (2015). Corporate Governance, Risk Disclosure Practices, and Market Liquidity: Comparative Evidence from the UK and Italy: Corporate Governance and Risk Disclosures. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 23(4), 331–356. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12095>
- Elzahar, H., & Hussainey, K. (2012). Determinants of narrative risk disclosures in UK interim reports. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 13(2), 133–147. <https://doi.org/10.1108/15265941211203189>
- Florackis, C. (2008). Agency costs and corporate governance mechanisms: Evidence for UK firms. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 4(1), 37–59. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17439130810837375>
- Gallery, G., Ma, J., & Buckby, S. (2015). An analysis of risk management disclosures: Australian evidence. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 30(8/9), 812–869. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-09-2013-0934>
- Ghazali, N. A. M. (2007). Ownership structure and corporate social responsibility disclosure: Some Malaysian evidence. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 7(3), 251–266. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14720700710756535>
- Hassan, B., Manaf Rosli Bin, A., & Amaran, A. (2008). Risk reporting: An exploratory study on risk management disclosure in Malaysian annual reports. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 24(1), 39–57. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900910919893>
- Kakanda, M. M., Salim, B., & Chandren, S. a/p. (2017). Corporate Governance, Risk Management Disclosure, and Firm Performance: A Theoretical and Empirical Review Perspective. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 7(9), 836–845. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2017.79.836.845>
- Khan, A. R., & Muttakin, M. B. (2013). *Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures: Evidence from An Emerging Economy*. 41.
- Khelif, H., & Hussainey, K. (2014). *The association between risk disclosure and firm characteristics: A meta-analysis* (Vol. 19). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2014.961514>
- Lajili, K. (2009). Corporate Risk Disclosure and Corporate Governance. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 2(1), 94–117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm2010094>
- Liao, G., & Lu, C. (2009). Ownership Structure and Corporate Voluntary Disclosure-Evidence from Taiwan. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv6i4p12>
- Lopes, P. T., & Rodrigues, L. L. (2007). Accounting for financial instruments: An analysis of the determinants of disclosure in the Portuguese stock

- exchange. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 42(1), 25–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intacc.2006.12.002>
- Ma, S., Naughton, T., & Tian, G. (2010). Ownership and ownership concentration: Which is important in determining the performance of China's listed firms? *Accounting & Finance*, 50(4), 871–897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-629X.2010.00353.x>
- Maghzom, A., Hussainey, K., & Aly, D. (2016). *Corporate Governance and Risk Disclosure: Evidence from Saudi Arabia*. 13(2).
- Maher, M., Stickney, C. P., & Weil, R. L. (2008). *Managerial accounting: An introduction to concepts, methods, and uses* (10th ed). Thomson/South-Western.
- Majeed, S., Aziz, T., & Saleem, S. (2015). The Effect of Corporate Governance Elements on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Disclosure: An Empirical Evidence from Listed Companies at KSE Pakistan. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 3(4), 530–556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs3040530>
- McKnight, P. J., & Weir, C. (2009). Agency costs, corporate governance mechanisms and ownership structure in large UK publicly quoted companies: A panel data analysis. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 49(2), 139–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2007.09.008>
- Mohamad, W. I. A. W., & Sulong, Z. (2010). Corporate governance mechanisms and extent of disclosure: Evidence from listed companies in Malaysia. *International Business Research*, 3(4), p216. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v3n4p216>
- Mohobbot, A. M. (2005). *Corporate risk reporting practices in annual reports of Japanese companies*.
- Moumen, N., Ben Othman, H., & Hussainey, K. (2016). Board structure and the informativeness of risk disclosure: Evidence from MENA emerging markets. *Advances in Accounting*, 35, 82–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adiac.2016.09.001>
- Mousa, G. A., & Elamir, E. A. H. (2013). *Content Analysis of Corporate Risk Disclosures: The Case of Bahraini Capital Market*. 29.
- Mustapha, M., & Che Ahmad, A. (2011). Agency theory and managerial ownership: Evidence from Malaysia. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 26(5), 419–436. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686901111129571>
- Namazi, M., & Kermani, E. (2013). An Empirical Investigation of the Relationship between Corporate Ownership Structures and their Performances (Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange). *Journal of Finance and Accounting*.
- Ntim, C. G., Lindop, S., & Thomas, D. A. (2013). Corporate governance and risk reporting in South Africa: A study of corporate risk disclosures in the pre-

- and post-2007/2008 global financial crisis periods. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 30, 363–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2013.07.001>
- OECD *Principles of Corporate Governance*. (2015).
- Prabowo, M., & Simpson, J. (2011). Independent directors and firm performance in family-controlled firms: Evidence from Indonesia: EVIDENCE FROM INDONESIA. *Asian-Pacific Economic Literature*, 25(1), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8411.2011.01276.x>
- Saggar, R., & Singh, B. (2017). Corporate governance and risk reporting: Indian evidence. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 32(4/5), 378–405. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-03-2016-1341>
- Said Mokhtar, E., & Mellett, H. (2013). Competition, corporate governance, ownership structure and risk reporting. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28(9), 838–865. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-11-2012-0776>
- Samaha, K., Azzam, I., & Khlif, H. (2015). Disclosure, ownership structure, earnings announcement lag and cost of equity capital in emerging markets: The case of the Egyptian stock exchange. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 16(1), 28–57. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAAR-06-2012-0046>
- Sarikhani, M., & Ebrahimi, M. (2011). Corporate Governance and Earnings Informativeness: Evidence from Iran. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. http://www.academia.edu/31248664/Corporate_Governance_and_Earnings_Informativeness_Evidence_from_Iran
- Scholten, M. (2014). *Ownership structure and firm performance*: 10.
- Shah, N., & Napier, C. J. (2015). *The Cadbury Report 1992: Shared Vision and Beyond*. 42.
- Shrives, P. J., & Linsley, P. M. (2006). Examining risk reporting in UK public companies. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 6(4), 292–305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/15265940510613633>
- Wang, Z., Al-Akra, M., & Ali, M. J. (2013). Value relevance of voluntary disclosure and the global financial crisis: Evidence from China. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28(5), 444–468. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686901311327218>
- Zabri, S. M., Ahmad, K., & Wah, K. K. (2016). Corporate Governance Practices and Firm Performance: Evidence from Top 100 Public Listed Companies in Malaysia. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35, 287–296. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00036-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00036-8)